

Spectrum of Pap smear Cytology According to Bethesda System**Rathwa Piyush¹, Sangada Pratibha², Adhwaryu Niti³, Jawarkar Ashish⁴**¹(R3), Parul Institute of Medical Sciences and Research (PIMSR)²(R2), Parul Institute of Medical Sciences and Research (PIMSR)³Senior Resident, Parul Institute of Medical Sciences and Research (PIMSR)⁴Head of the Department and Professor, Parul Institute of Medical Sciences and Research (PIMSR)

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Abstract:

Introduction: Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cause of death and morbidity for women worldwide. It is the second most common malignancy in India between ages 15-44 years. The gold standard screening test for early diagnosis of cervical epithelial cell abnormalities, mild to severe dysplasia, precancerous cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and the early stage of invasive cervical cancer is the Pap smear.

Aims and objectives: To Evaluation of spectrum of Pap smear cytology according to Bethesda system and to assess the usefulness of the cytological study in the diagnosis of cervical lesions.

Material and Methodology: Retrospective study of 400 cases of Pap smear verified by microscopic examination by expert pathologists in the department of pathology at PSH from April 2023 to August 2023.

Result: In our study the results is divided into categories: NILM and Epithelial cell abnormality. In NILM Inflammatory smear, NILM with Bacterial vaginosis and NILM with trichomonas vaginalis were included. In Epithelial cell abnormality ASCUS, HSIL, LSIL, ASC-H, SCC and AGUS were included.

Conclusion: Pap smear is proven tested tool for making an early diagnosis and treating cervical cancer in early stage. Thus, Pap smear is simple, less expensive diagnostic tool suitable for implementation in India.

Keywords: PAP, NILM, AGUS, ASCUS, LSIL, HSIL, ASC-H.

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Introduction

Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cause of death and morbidity for women worldwide [1]. It is the second most common malignancy in India between ages 15-44 years [2]. Nearly 6,04,000 new cases and 3,42,000 fatalities worldwide were reported in 2020 for developing countries [1]. Due to a lack of efficient screening programs and a lack of awareness of the symptoms of cervical cancer, India has a high prevalence of the disease [3]. The pre-invasive stage of cervical cancer is very protracted and can be detected early on. Early detection and treatment of precancerous lesions can reduce mortality [4].

Cervical screening reduced the occurrence of cervical cancer. Therefore, cytological screening with a pap smear can be used to detect precursor lesions in the cervix early (6). The gold standard screening test for early diagnosis of cervical epithelial cell abnormalities, mild to severe dysplasia, precancerous cervical intraepithelial neoplasia and the early stage of invasive cervical cancer is the Pap smear [5]. The diagnosis of bacterial and inflammatory disorders, including the determination of the causative organism, hormone-related benign epithelial alterations and changes

due to therapeutic agents are all greatly aided by pap smears [3]. Pap smear is a low-cost, simple, safe, and uncomplicated procedure for identifying precancerous lesions in females [5].

The Bethesda System was created in 1988 and updated in 1991, 2001 and 2014 respectively. It contains aspects like specimen type, specimen adequacy, general categorization, interpretation and other elements such as ancillary testing, computer assisted interpretation, educational notes and comments [6]. Even though Pap smear is gold standard screening test but Indian guideline for cervical screening include only visual inspection of cervix.

Methodology

This is cross sectional study of 400 pap smears received in cytology department of pathology from April 2023 to September 2023. Cervical smears were taken at obstetrics and gynaecology opd by using conventional method of cervical cytology. Pap smears were taken from the transformation zone with use of Ayre's spatula rapidly, stroked gently and evenly spread on glass slide. These smears were fix in isopropyl alcohol and stain by

Papanicolaou staining method. The new Bethesda classification for cervical cytology reporting 2014 was used to evaluate the cytological results of the smear. The following is the 2014 Bethesda system for reporting cervical cytology:

1. Specimen type.
2. Specimen adequacy.
3. Interpretation.
4. Negative for intraepithelial lesion or malignancy.
5. Other.

Pap stain is multichrome counter stain method, based on dye competition in the cytoplasm combined with a nuclear haematoxylin staining. It consists of nuclear stain haematoxylin and two cytoplasmic stains OG-6.

Results

Table 1: Age Wise Distribution

Age	NILIM	Inflammation	ASCUS	LSIL	HSIL	ASC-H	AGUS	SCC
	n=330	n=306	n=02	n=15	n=10	n=01	n=01	n=01
21-30	10	200	00	01	00	00	00	00
31-40	281	56	00	01	03	00	00	00
41-50	22	20	02	11	05	00	00	00
51-60	12	15	00	01	02	01	01	01
61-70	3	10	00	01	00	00	00	00
>70	2	05	00	00	00	00	00	00

Table 2: Distribution of NILM

Result	No of cases
Inflammation	306 (92.73%)
Inflammation with <i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i>	10 (3.03%)
Inflammation with bacterial vaginosis	14 (4.24%)

Table 3: Distribution of Epithelial Cell Abnormality

Result of Epithelial cell abnormality	No of cases
ASCUS	02(6.67%)
LSIL	15(50%)
HSIL	10(33.33%)
ASC-H	1(3.33%)
AGUS	1(3.33%)
SCC	1(3.33%)

Discussion

In present study, maximum cases 330 (91.67%) revealed NILM morphology and 30(8.33%) cases revealed Epithelial cell abnormality on PAP smear evaluation by Bethesda system of reporting. Predominant Epithelial cell abnormality in present study was LSIL. Percentage of ASCUS, LSIL, HSIL ASC-H, SCC and AGUS 6.67%, 50%, 33.33%, 3.33%, 3.33% and 3.33% respectively in present study. The American cancer society has given new screening guidelines for cervical cancer that all women should begin cervical cancer screening for cervical cancer screening at age of

Out of 400 pap smears, 360(90%) were satisfactory and 40 (10%) were unsatisfactory for evaluation. Out of 360 cases, 330(91.67%) NILM, 30(8.33%) with epithelial cell abnormality.

Out of 330 cases with NILM, Inflammation was seen in 306(92.73%), NILM with *trichomonas vaginalis* was seen in 10(3.03%) and NILM with bacterial vaginosis was seen in 14 (4.24%).

Out of 30 cases with epithelial cell abnormality, AS-CUS was seen in 02 (6.67%), LSIL in 15(50%), HSIL in 10 (33.33%), ASC-H in 1 (3.33%), SCC in 1(3.33%) and AGUS in 1(3.33%) patient.

Cases of LSIL and HSIL are more commonly seen in the age group of 41-50 years.

21[1]. Women between the ages of 21 and 29 should have a Pap test every 3 years [1].

They should not be tested for HPV unless it is needed after an abnormal Pap test result. Women between the ages of 30 and 65 should have both a Pap test and an HPV test every 5 years [2]. Women over age 65 who have had regular screenings with normal results should not be screened for cervical cancer.

Women who have been diagnosed with cervical pre-cancer should continue to be screened [3]. Women who are at high risk of cervical cancer may need to be screened more often. Women at high

risk might include those with HIV infection, organ transplant or exposure to the drug [4].

Figure 1: Inflammatory Smear

Figure 2: ASCUS

Figure 3: LSIL

Figure 4: HSIL

Figure 5: ASC-H

Figure 6: AGUS

Figure 6: SCC

Conclusion

Pap smear is proven tested tool for making an early diagnosis and treating cervical cancer in early stage. Thus, pap smear is simple, less expensive screening tool suitable for implementation in India. Pap smear testing is a very useful, simple, economical, and safe tool for detecting precancerous cervical epithelial lesions. With the use of Pap smear as a screening tool for detection of abnormal epithelial lesions in cervix, more cases can be diagnosed early and thus morbidity and mortality of patients can be decreased. By proper implementation of Pap screening programme, incidence of invasive cervical malignancy can be prevented due to early detection of cervical premalignant lesions.

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